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Conference Abstract

A RESEARCH ANALYSIS OF THE STYLES OF SIRAH WRITING OF DR. MUHAMMAD HAMIDULLAH AND MAULANA SYED ABUL ALA MAUDUDI

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative research analysis of the styles of Sirah (Prophetic biography) writing of Dr. Muhammad Hamidullah and Maulana Syed Abul Ala Maududi. Both figures made significant contributions to the study of the Sirah of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) in the twentieth century; however, their perspectives, methodologies of research, and styles of expression exhibit distinct differences. Dr. Hamidullah, a renowned researcher and legal scholar, examines the events of the Sirah based on historical and documentary evidence, adopting a scholarly and research-oriented approach. His emphasis lies on collecting authentic narrations, scrutinizing their chain of transmission, and understanding events within their historical and geographical context. In contrast, Maulana Maududi, a thinker, reformer, and the founder of the Islamic movement, presents the Sirah of the Prophet (peace be upon him) as a comprehensive system of life and a practical model. His style is primarily motivational and reformatory in nature. He derives principles and lessons from the events of the Sirah and presents them as guidance for resolving contemporary issues. Maulana Maududi does not view the Sirah merely as a narrative of historical events but rather as a dynamic force capable of reforming individuals and society. The paper will also analyze the common aspects of their works and the reasons for their divergence. The aim of this research is to understand how these two styles have influenced the study and understanding of the Sirah of the Prophet (peace be upon him) in the Indian subcontinent and globally, and what

guiding principles they offer for future Sirah writing. This paper emphasizes that both styles hold their own significance for a comprehensive study of the Sirah, and their synthesis can lead to a more complete and effective understanding.

Keywords: *Maulana Syed Abul Ala Maududi, Muhammad Hamidulla, Siraha writing, Comparative analysis, Research-oriented style, Authentic narrations.*

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